

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

TEACHER EMPOWERMENT IN THE ARMENIAN EVANGELICAL SCHOOLS
OF LEBANON: TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the

Requirements for the Degree

Master of Arts in Educational Leadership

by

Nara V. Kouzikian

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To my daughter Galya.

Praying this will be an inspiration for you to always challenge yourself.

THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Arts in Educational Leadership

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Title: TEACHER EMPOWERMENT IN THE ARMENIAN EVANGELICAL
SCHOOLS OF LEBANON: TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS

Researcher: Nara V. Kouzikian

Advisor: John Issa, PHD

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Teacher empowerment has been an important topic in recent studies. Teacher empowerment is closely linked to teacher motivation and student achievement, and it can be divided to six dimensions according to Short and Rinehart (1992): (a) status, (b) professional growth, (c) self-efficacy, (d) decision-making, (e) impact, and (f) autonomy.

The study followed a mixed-method approach to examine the levels of teacher empowerment in the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon, to compare teachers' perceived levels of empowerment to the principals' perceptions of teacher empowerment, and to find, if any, a significant relationship between teacher empowerment and teacher attributes (gender, years of experience, and level of education).

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APPROVAL BY THE COMMITTEE:

Advisor: John Issa, PhD

Reader: Shawna Vyhmeister, PhD

Dean: John Issa, PhD

Date approved

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The *Oxford Dictionary* defines “empowerment” as “authority or power given to someone to do something” and “the process of becoming stronger and more confident, especially in controlling one’s life and claiming one’s rights.” The *Business Dictionary* considers it “a management practice of sharing information, rewards, and power with employees so that they can take initiative and make decisions to solve problems to improve service and performance.” The word “empowerment” has been used in different contexts in recent world history from empowering African-Americans to empowering women to empowering students. In the world of management, this word refers to granting employees control over certain aspects of their jobs.

People have now come to understand the importance of education and that educating children is one way of empowering them and showing them how to have control over their lives and prerogatives. If education aims to empower students, then teachers are the chief catalysts who can change the world one student at a time because “it is not farfetched to conceive of teachers as change agents. They are already part way there. Teachers as change agents are the sine qua non of getting anywhere” (Fullan, 1993, p. 18).

If teachers are authority figures in the classroom and responsible for empowering and helping students grow academically, emotionally, physically, and morally, it is only fair that they themselves feel empowered in their jobs. It is only fair

that they be given authority in certain aspects of their jobs. Therefore, one of the essential duties of school administrations should be to ensure high levels of teacher empowerment.

The expectations the public has placed on schools make it necessary for schools to introduce certain changes. Therefore, the school leadership is compelled to shift from a top-down approach in management to a participative approach where teachers have a voice, especially since many of school-related decisions affect them and their students directly.

Statement of the Problem

Often times, teachers are not given a voice in important decisions in schools, especially decisions that directly affect them or their students. Some might not feel that what they are doing is influential, and they might even believe that they do not enjoy the professional respect they deserve. Others might feel that they do not have appropriate opportunities for professional growth.

Since teacher empowerment is an important issue because it can consequently affect the students, school administrators should make sure teachers are in fact empowered. However, administrators are often unaware of their teachers' perception of empowerment and might even think that teachers are empowered when they are not. At other times, administrators might not even consider teacher empowerment an important aspect in school success. Without an understanding of the teachers' perspective, it is difficult for administrators to empower them.

Purpose of the Study

The current study (a) aimed to measure the extent to which teachers in the five Armenian Evangelical schools in Lebanon feel empowered on six dimensions of

empowerment, and it (b) compared the teachers' perception of their empowerment to the administrators' perception of the teachers' empowerment in an attempt to bring perspectives together.

Research Questions

To understand how empowerment is perceived by teachers and administrators in the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon, I wanted to answer the following questions during this study:

1. What are the teachers' perceptions of their own levels of empowerment, as measured by The School Participant Empowerment Scale (Short & Rinehart, 1992)?
2. Does gender, level of education, or years of experience play a role in teachers' overall perceptions of empowerment?
3. Do the teachers and the principals of the Armenian Evangelical schools have similar perceptions of teacher empowerment?
4. How do the principals view teacher empowerment in the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon?

Significance of the Study

This study intends to give the principals of the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon an insight, for the first time, into the teachers' perception of their own levels of empowerment. Moreover, it can be a helpful guide with preliminary suggestions that can be the groundwork upon which administrators can create their own plan of action to ensure higher degrees of empowerment for their teachers in the future.

Rationale

As a teacher, I have experienced first-hand the importance of motivation and empowerment in the workplace, namely schools. I have quit a teaching job because I did not feel empowered. At the time, I could only explain my feelings as frustration. As I started reading about teacher empowerment, I began to understand that my frustration was because I was not empowered in that job; I did not have a voice.

Furthermore, as a Lebanese citizen of Armenian origins with an Evangelical background, I wanted my research paper to be of benefit to the community I belong to, which is the Armenian Evangelical community in Lebanon. For these two reasons, this study has been undertaken and involves the teachers and the principals of the Armenian Evangelical schools of Lebanon.

Definitions

Teacher Empowerment: Teacher empowerment is used in a generic way in this study to refer to a social process that helps teachers gain control over some important aspects of their professional lives. More specific definitions are provided in the literature review chapter.

School Participant Empowerment Scale: The School Participant Empowerment Scale (SPES) (Short & Rinehart, 1992) is an instrument which measures teacher empowerment on six dimensions: (a) status, (b) professional growth, (c) self-efficacy, (d) decision-making, (e) impact, and (f) autonomy.

Administrators, Principals, and Supervisors: The words “administrators,” “supervisors” and “principals” are used interchangeably in this study to refer to figures of authority in schools.

Professional Growth: “Professional growth” and “professional development” are terms used interchangeably to refer to the opportunities given to teachers to expand their job-related skills.

CHAPTER 2
REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Definitions and History

In recent world history, the word “empowerment” has been used more frequently in different domains; however, a quick review of related literature indicates that there is no agreement on one definition of empowerment that fits different fields. Empowerment is a concept shared by many disciplines such as psychology, education, economics, business, and social studies, among others.

Potterfield (1999) explains in his book that in the 1950s and 1960s, empowerment was considered an attempt to create more democratic and participatory administrations in companies, and empowerment programs were initiated to try “to enhance employee motivation, increase efficiency, and gain competitive advantage in the turbulent contemporary business environment” (p. 6).

For Rappaport (1985), empowerment is understood “at the level of feelings, at the level of ideas about self-worth, at the level of being able to make a difference in the world around us” (p. 15). However, it can be achieved by giving the employee the opportunity and the ability to take control of some important areas of his or her daily work (Rappaport, 1985).

Dunst (1991) in his presentation at the annual meeting of Children’s Mental Health and Service Policy convention, stated that empowerment consists primarily of 1) providing facilitating experiences within an organization that foster autonomy,

choice, control, and responsibility and 2) offering employees the opportunity to present their competencies and acquire new competencies.

Empowerment in the workplace is extremely beneficial for the organization because employees who feel they have certain amount of “freedom, autonomy and discretion, feel personally connected to the organization, and feel confident about their abilities and capable of having an impact on the organization” (Sahoo & Das, 2011, p. 47). Moreover, employee creativity increases in the presence of empowering leadership according to a 2016 study especially when empowering leadership is combined with employee intrinsic motivation and task visibility, which is the employee’s belief that his or her effort is visible by the employer (Byun, Dai, Lee, & Kang, 2016).

The authors of the article *The Relationship between The Practices of Leadership Style and Teacher Empowerment of Headmasters in the Primary Schools* consider empowerment a new way of working together:

It entails encouraging people to become more involved in making decisions and implementing activities that can affect their work. It provides individuals the opportunity to come up with good ideas. At the same time, it involves trusting that these individuals have the skills to put their ideas into practice. (Fook, Rosidih, & Keang, 2017, p. 59)

In *Leadership as Stewardship*, Sergiovanni (2007) states that “empowerment derives its full strength from being linked to purposing: everyone is free to do what makes sense, as long as people’s decisions embody the values shared by the school community” (p. 54). He then discusses the difference between the terms “power over” and “power to”:

“Power over” emphasizes controlling what people do, when they do it, and how they do it. “Power to” views power as a source of energy for achieving shared goals and purposes. Indeed, when empowerment is successfully practiced, administrators exchange “power over” to “power to.” “Power over” is rule-bound, but “power to” is goal bound. (p. 57)

Even though there is no agreement on one definition of empowerment, most of the definitions above consider employee involvement or partaking in decision-making coupled with a certain degree of freedom at work important in cultivating feelings of empowerment in employees.

Psychological Empowerment

Psychological empowerment is another term used in this context, and it “describes how the intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy of people are influenced by leadership behavior, job characteristics, organization structure, and their needs and values” (Yukl, 2011, pp. 135-136).

According to the article *Psychological Empowerment in the Workplace: Dimensions, Measurement, and Validations*, psychological empowerment is a motivational concept demonstrated in four different dimensions: 1) meaning, which involves a fit between the requirements of the task and the employees’ own beliefs and values, 2) self-determination, which is autonomy and decision-making 3) self-efficacy, which is the employee’s belief in his or her abilities and skills, and 4) impact, which is the employee’s influence in the workplace. As such, a simple delegation of tasks or a trivial decision made by the employees is not enough for a true sense of empowerment (Spreitzer, 1995). Spreitzer (1995) also discusses the two benefits of psychological empowerment in the workplace: effectiveness and innovation.

Teacher Empowerment

School teachers, as employees at an organization, also need to experience empowerment in their workplace. According to Melenyzer (1990), as the United States of America moved toward educational reform starting in the 1980s with *A Nation at Risk*, there was a call for an increased top down approach. It was clear that teachers' involvement was of utmost importance. Therefore, the teacher was to be given a voice in decision making to achieve this reform. In fact, "the National Education Association (NEA), the American Federation of teachers (AFT), and the United Federation of Teachers (UFT) have proclaimed teacher empowerment as a goal at the local, state, and national levels" (Melenyzer, 1990, p. 10).

Teacher empowerment can be defined as "a process whereby school participants develop the competence to take charge of their own growth and resolve their own problems" (Short, 1994). Teacher empowerment consists of improved status, increased knowledge, and partaking in decision-making (Maeroff, 1988). Short (1994) explains that empowered schools should "create opportunities for competence to be developed and displayed" (p. 488).

Six Dimensions of Teacher Empowerment

In their paper, Short and Rinehart (1992) present six dimensions of teacher empowerment which are (a) status, (b) professional growth, (c) self-efficacy, (d) decision-making, (e) impact, and (f) autonomy. This study is based on these dimensions, which may provide guidelines for principals to develop strategies that will help teachers become more empowered in their work lives.

Status

According to Short (1994), “status as a dimension of empowerment refers to teacher perceptions that they have professional respect and admiration from colleagues” (p. 490). Furthermore, all teachers “are at their best in the classroom when they are supported by their colleagues in appreciatively supportive ways to know how best to improve and integrate their practice” (Bills, Giles, & Rogers, 2016, p. 118).

Status is closely linked to professionalism “for teacher empowerment means_ more than anything else_ working in an environment in which the teacher acts and is treated as a professional” (Maeroff, *The Principles of Teacher Empowerment*, 1989, p. 6). As a consequence, teachers start to build professional learning communities within their schools by collaborating with each other (Harris, 2003).

Unfortunately, teachers fear their status is becoming tainted because society is losing faith in the education system. The unnecessary paperwork, poor facilities, high expectations from society, and low opinions of teachers are effecting teacher status negatively. Teachers have been reporting hearing complaints more than compliments. (Short, 1994)

In their book, Blase and Kirby (2009) consider verbal praise an effective method principals may utilize to boost teachers’ esteem and make them feel respected for the competent professionals that they are.

Professional Growth

Professional growth means providing teachers with opportunities to grow, learn continuously, and expand their skills (Short & Rinehart, 1992).

Bills, Giles, and Rogers (2016) highlight the preposition “in” when they discuss professional development; they explain that it is important to say that teachers

are “in” professional learning, considering professional development an essential part of and an ongoing process in a teacher’s professional experience and career.

“Accordingly, teacher education programs and school professional development approaches need to assist and evoke pre-service student teachers and beginning teachers towards a deeper appreciation and sensitivity to their way of being in teaching and professional learning” (p. 119). They also differentiate between knowledge and teaching: “We know that beginning teachers need to have a professional knowledge of teaching (knowing) and professional practices in teaching (doing)” (p. 118).

However, professional development practices are not always viewed as positive practices by teachers. In-service teachers do not participate in professional development workshops with much enthusiasm because often times these workshops are planned or even prepared by administrators without taking into consideration the individual needs of the teachers in their profession. Administrators, on the other hand, view these same workshops as excellent opportunities given to teachers to grow professionally and expand their skills that pertain to their jobs (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007).

Moreover, teachers might consider promotion to be one form of professional growth. A promotion can be considered a formal path of professional growth while workshops and learning opportunities can be considered an informal path as Helterbran (2010) explains in *Teacher Leadership: Overcoming the I Am Just a Teacher Syndrome*:

For the teacher, there are numerous formal and informal avenues to express leadership. The most familiar are the traditional, formal, and hierarchical roles in a school which may include departmental or grade level chair, subject area

supervisor, mentor, or various instructional coaching roles. These important positions come replete with a job description and formal expectations; they also typically are associated with release time or monetary compensation. The other, more informal and emergent, type of teacher leadership runs much deeper, is self-generated, and holds the promise of serving as a mechanism for continual professional learning and innovation in the school. (p. 365)

Helterbran (2010), however, states that “teacher leadership, in its truest sense, involves those informal aspects of leadership” (p. 365). As such, she accentuates the importance of those workshops, seminars, and learning opportunities teachers have as a means of growing professionally.

Sergiovanni and Starratt (2007) consider teacher involvement in professional development very essential. They suggest this involvement start as early as the planning stage of professional development programs. They propose “involving teachers in problem solving and action research. Teachers and supervisors share responsibility for the planning, development, and provision of staff development activities, and the focus is much less on training than on puzzling, inquiring, and solving problems” (p. 216).

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy refers to the teacher’s belief that he or she has the skills and ability to help students learn (Short & Rinehart, 1992). Bandura (1997), a pioneer in efficacy theories, argues that people (teachers) with strong self-efficacy beliefs welcome new challenges, while those who have weak self-efficacy beliefs in performing certain tasks may experience stress and feelings of burnout. He also discusses collective efficacy as being “the groups’ shared belief in its conjoint

capabilities to organize and execute courses of action required to produce given levels of attainments” (p. 477).

Brinson and Steiner (2007) emphasize the importance of collective efficacy in schools and its positive effect on improved student performance. They claim that this collective efficacy can be built “by providing teachers with opportunities to build instructional knowledge and collaborate with colleagues, with feedback that is insightful, and with a vision of success in which teachers are treated as sources of expertise” (p. 5). Furthermore, according to a 2016 study, workers with high self-efficacy experience success not only on the job by working more efficiently and producing better results, but also in other fields of life such as academic achievements and health goals (Agarwal & Mishra, 2016).

One recent study (Caprara, Barbaranelli, Steca, & Malone, 2006) explored the effects of teachers’ perceived self-efficacy. The researchers found that the teachers’ self-efficacy was positively linked to students’ motivation and academic achievement, as well as their own satisfaction on the job.

According to a case study by Milner and Hoy (2002), “self-efficacy affects the effort teachers invest in teaching, the goals they set, and their level of aspiration. Teachers with a strong sense of efficacy are open to new ideas and are more willing to experiment with new methods to better meet the needs of their students” (p. 4).

Decision-Making

Decision-making refers to the teachers’ active partaking in decisions that affect their work such as decisions about curriculum and material taught (Short & Rinehart, 1992).

Decision-making sometimes involves change, and school administrations are usually behind those changes. However, according to a 2016 article that promotes

“teacher-powered schools,” there is a movement toward considering teachers “agents of change rather than the targets of it” (Berry & Farris-Berg, 2016, p. 12). These authors argue that students attain better learning outcomes if their teachers are making important decisions that involve the school and the students:

Keeping students at the center of their decisions, they make choices about a wide array of factors, including the design of the instructional program and professional development, colleague selection, budgeting, and whether to give (and how much to count) district assessments. In many teacher-powered schools, teachers also evaluate their colleagues through peer review processes, as is often the case in other professions. (Berry & Farris-Berg, 2016, p. 15)

In terms of decisions about curriculum, Wa Ho (2010) suggests a shift in teachers’ roles from curriculum users to curriculum leaders, and it also suggests teachers work collaboratively to that end. Wa Ho (2010) concludes by stating that since teachers have the professional knowledge and experience to provide for the educational needs of students, they can also make decisions about the curriculum to ensure it meets the needs and interests of students.

Short (1994) explains that a school climate should be designed in such a way as to promote openness and risk taking to encourage teachers to participate in decision-making and trying new ideas and methods by taking risks. According to Leech and Fulton (2008), “one variable affecting the implementation of shared decision making or teacher empowerment is the concept of willingness--the principal's willingness to empower and the teacher's willingness to participate” (Leech & Fulton, 2008, p. 635).

Impact

Impact as a dimension of empowerment is the teachers' belief that they have an influence on school life, that they are doing something meaningful, and that they are acknowledged for their accomplishments. Acknowledging teacher effort or even recognizing student achievement as a result of teacher effort would give the teachers a sense of empowerment (Short, 1994).

Teachers' perceptions of how they are valued and supported by their school leader/principal often affect their daily decisions to motivate students and encourage them toward academic achievement (Demir, 2008). This means that when school leaders make teacher support and appreciation central to the school culture, the students' academic achievement improves as a result (Williams, 2006).

In *The Drive to Influence* (2017), Rodriguez shares his belief that the urge to influence learners and to develop them is at the core of the teaching profession. Ashton and Webb (1986) explain that when teachers feel that they are doing something valuable with proficiency and are recognized for it, their self-esteem is boosted and they believe they have an impact on school life.

Teacher impact or influence can also be translated through teacher collaboration. Experienced teachers can teach novice teachers; and subsequently, novice teachers report effective on the job-learning (Jackson & Bruegmann, 2009), and experienced teachers will have some level of influence on school life and feel empowered.

Additionally, empowered teachers have the ability to influence the culture of the school in a positive manner. This positive affect of teacher leader efforts can lead to a school culture that includes ongoing learning for all (Roby, 2011).

Autonomy

Teacher autonomy is the teachers' belief that they have certain control in some areas of their work (Short & Rinehart, 1992). In their book *Trusting Teachers with School Success: What Happens When Teachers Call the Shots* (2012), Farris-Berg, Dirkswager, and Junge discuss the importance of autonomy:

The teacher autonomy strategy is about giving groups of teachers—the professionals who work most closely with the students—the opportunity to choose, even invent, the learning methods and job structures they think will best improve learning for the students at their schools. (p. 11)

However, Short and Rinehart (1992) also draw attention to the issue of accountability as an important constituent of granting teachers autonomy. Teachers are not to be told how to meet the educational goals or what to do in class but are to be held accountable for their decisions, assuming “that because teachers are professionals, they know how to meet them” (Farris-Berg, Dirkswager, & Junge, 2012, p. 11).

Ryan and Deci (2000) discovered in their study that autonomy (along with competence and relatedness) is one of the basic psychological needs of human beings, and the fulfillment of these needs leads to improved intrinsic motivation and good mental health. In contrast, a lack of teacher autonomy is associated with feelings of powerlessness among teachers, and this can result in distress and anxiety (Mayer, Donaldson, LeChasseur, Welton, & Cobb, 2013).

Teacher Burnout

Teachers who do not feel empowered at school and have decreased levels of job satisfaction may eventually experience psychological burnout. This burnout can be defined as “a psychological syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization,

and reduced personal accomplishment” (Maslach, Jackson, & Leither, 1996, p. 192).

Emotional exhaustion refers to teachers’ feeling that they are drained emotionally, that they cannot fulfill the requirements of the job as they did before, and that they have nothing left to contribute to the workplace (Maslach & Jackson, 1984).

Depersonalization refers to the negative attitudes teachers develop toward colleagues or even students, and this can sometimes be manifested through the use of offensive or cynical language (Maslach & Pines, 1977). Finally, reduced personal accomplishment occurs when teachers begin to view and evaluate themselves negatively and feel incompetent. Eventually, their contribution to the workplace is reduced (Maslach & Jackson, 1984).

Unfortunately, teacher burnout does not only affect the teachers on a personal or emotional level, but it can have negative consequences on the educational institution they belong to because “burnout can lead to a deterioration in the quality of care or service provided by the staff. It appears to be a factor in job turnover, absenteeism, and low morale” (Maslach, Jackson, & Leither, 1996, p. 193)

Furthermore, teacher burnout can influence the students:

As teacher burnout increases, both the thoroughness of classroom preparation and the involvement in classroom activities decline while student criticism increases. In response, students are likely to change their perception of the teacher, their feelings towards the teacher, and their behavior in the classroom. Consequently, students’ sense of efficacy in school often declines.

Furthermore, teacher burnout reduces students’ intrinsic motivation, which may diminish learning and engagement. (Shen, et al., 2015, p. 520)

As such, empowering teachers can be beneficial to the teachers, the students, and the educational institution as a whole. According to Short and Johnson (1994),

“empowered workers contribute more to the profit motives of the company at less cost” (p. 3), and, in an educational institution, empowered teachers are more effective and can improve student achievement as well as school environment (Short & Johnson, 1994).

The Role of the Principal

Even though Sharma (2014) says “the teacher is the key agent in the transition to this new vision of education” (p. 1), he does not think empowering teachers is a process in which teachers change their own beliefs, attitudes, and practices. He explains that “beliefs and attitudes change at the level of a community rather than at the level of an individual teacher” (p. 1). Therefore, school administrators should design their practices in such a way that ensures higher degrees of teacher empowerment. This should be a priority for school administrators because a teacher’s perception of his or her empowerment is positively linked to professional commitment, commitment to the organization, and satisfaction with the job (Ahmed, Malik, Sajjad, Hyder, & Hussain, 2014) which eventually affects the students’ academic performance positively (Marks & Louis, 1997).

Sahoo and Das (2011) explain that empowerment requires more than giving a certain amount of power to employees; it requires some considerations from management:

The feeling of employee empowerment can be improved by listening and being more responsive to employee comments, providing necessary training, encouragement by management and fellow employees, providing employees with the necessary resources to do their jobs, allowing access to relevant information and matching employees to their tasks according to training and experience. (p. 47)

Sahoo and Das (2011) conclude their article by relating employee empowerment to employee involvement in the organization, and they explain that because of employee empowerment, “employees are not managed by the traditional hierarchical control system, instead, out of their commitment towards shared organizational goals, as they enforce self-discipline to achieve these” (p. 51).

In ideal situations, the idea of teacher involvement is not limited to a few decisions or committee votes. Terry (1999) suggests that “outstanding principals go beyond merely involving teachers in decision-making.” He believes principals should employ three strategies to empower teachers:

(a) provide a supportive environment that encourages teachers to examine and reflect upon their teaching and on school practice; (b) use specific behaviors to facilitate reflective practice; and (c) make it possible for teachers to implement ideas and programs that result from reflective practice. (Terry, 1999, p. 7)

According to the findings of a study conducted by Hughes, Matt, and O’Reilly (2015) principals play a significant role in teacher retention in hard-to-staff schools through empowering the teachers:

Personal growth and the ability to receive support from administrators regarding emotional, environmental and instructional support had an impact on a teacher’s decision to stay or leave in hard-to-staff schools. The value of communication and being notified of events in their buildings was also very important to the teachers. This type of support, emotional, environmental and instructional, points to the notion that respondents want to be valued within the school system. (p. 132)

In the book *Empowerment Takes More Than a Minute* (Blanchard, Carlos & Alan, 1996), ownership is an important concept. The authors link the idea of

ownership to empowerment through the words of a character in the book, the Empowering Manager. This manager explains to a struggling manager that when employees feel that they own the business, they feel empowered and work harder. According to her, it is not true that employees are unable to give their best in the workplace but that they are afraid because “most organizations are set up to catch people doing things wrong rather than to encourage and reward them for doing things right” (p. 14). Therefore, employers must find a way to make employees adopt ownership of the business and release the power employees have within by creating an environment that promotes creativity and collaboration (Blanchard, Carlos, & Alan, 1996).

Principals need to be proactive in making sure teachers work in an environment that helps them feel empowered. In his article *Empowering Teachers as Leaders*, Terry (1999) accentuates the role of principals in teacher empowerment and states that “it is essential that a principal create an environment conducive to empowerment, demonstrates empowerment ideals, encourages all endeavors toward empowerment, and applauds all empowerment successes” (p. 2).

It is also important that principals find hidden talents especially in teachers who are not always in the spotlight. Lumpkin, Claxton, and Wilson (2014) summarize the role of the principal in empowering teachers in their article *Key Characteristics of Teacher Leaders in Schools*:

The principal needs to search for hidden teacher leadership talents, nurture these talents, and empower teacher leaders to flourish. Principals must create time for teacher leaders, develop interdependent teaching roles, give teachers a voice in decisions, and foster opportunities to expand their expertise. (p. 63)

Leadership Styles and Empowerment

There are different leadership styles school administrators may adopt as their own starting from authoritative styles where the principal has the most authority to participative styles where the power is shared with the teachers. Three of the main leadership styles are laissez-faire leadership, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership.

Laissez-faire Leadership. The laissez-faire leadership approach is described as a leader's indifference about the assignment or task at hand or the followers; it is "the absence of effective leadership" (Yukl, 2011, p. 314). It is considered the most inactive or ineffective type of leadership where necessary decisions are not made promptly because of the absence of the leader (Bass & Riggio, 2006).

Skogstad, Einarsen, Torsheim, Aasland, and Hetland (2002) have concluded after their study that the laissez-faire leadership is not only ineffective but downright destructive as it can lead to interpersonal problems in the workplace, which ultimately effect the organization. . In another study conducted in 2014, the authors associated laissez-faire leadership with employee stress and concluded that "the avoidance of leadership responsibilities in leader-follower relationships, in the form of laissez-faire leadership, may thus be decisive in explaining subordinates' experience of work-related stress" (Skogstad et al., 2014, p. 335).

Transactional Leadership. Transactional leadership motivates followers to recognize what needs to be done and to do it in exchange for personal benefits such as recognition or increase in salary (Leithwood, 1992). Bass and Riggio (2006) define this type of leadership as based on transaction or exchange where the leader discusses what needs to be done and specifies the conditions and rewards simultaneously. As such, "transactional leaders recognize followers' needs and desires and clarify how

those needs and desires will be met in exchange for enactment of the followers' work role" (Jung & Sosik, 2002, p. 316). This type of leadership depends on reinforcement, which "can be materialistic or symbolic, immediate or delayed, partial or whole, implicit or explicit, and involve rewards or resources" (Jogulu & Wood, 2007).

Yukl (2011) explains that a transactional leader exhibits three types of transactional behavior: "contingent reward, passive management by exception, and active management by exception" (p. 13). He then elaborates on each behavior:

Contingent reward behavior includes clarification of accomplishments necessary to obtain rewards, and the use of incentives to influence subordinate task motivation. Passive management by exception includes use of contingent punishments and other corrective action in response to obvious deviation from acceptable performance standards. Another transactional behavior called active management by exception...is defined in terms of looking for mistakes and enforcing rules to avoid mistakes. (Yukl, 2011, pp. 313-314)

Transformational Leadership. A definition of transformational leadership is that "transformational leadership appeals to the moral values of followers in an attempt to raise their consciousness about ethical issues and to mobilize their energy and resources to reform institutions" (Yukl, 2011, p. 312). Another explanation of transformational leadership is given by Jung and Sossik (2002): "transformational leaders create a group environment where followers feel empowered to seek an innovative approach to perform their job without a fear of being penalized" (p. 317). This type of leadership often motivates others to do more than they had intended or even thought possible by setting high expectations (Bass & Riggio, 2006).

This type of leader shows interest in the followers. Bass and Riggio (2006) mention in their book that transformational leaders usually have "more committed and

satisfied followers,” and they “empower followers and pay attention to their individual needs and personal development, helping followers to develop their own leadership potential” (p. 4).

In his article, Leithwood (1992) refers to his and his colleagues’ previous studies on leadership and states that “transformational school leaders are in more or less continuous pursuit of three fundamental goals: 1) helping staff members develop and maintain a collaborative, professional school culture; 2) fostering teacher development; and 3) helping them solve problems together more effectively” (pp. 9-10). As such, the emphasis is on relationships in the workplace.

Yukl (2011) states that the transformational leader exhibits four types of behavior: “idealized behavior, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and inspirational motivation” (p. 313). He then explains each behavior:

Idealized influence is behavior that increases follower identification with the leader, such as setting an example of courage and dedication and making self-sacrifices to benefit followers. Intellectual stimulation is behavior that influences followers to view problems from a new perspective and look for more creative solutions. Individualized consideration includes providing support, encouragement, and coaching to followers. A revision of the theory added another transformational behavior called inspirational motivation, which includes communicating an appealing vision and using symbols to focus subordinate effort. (p. 313)

The individual relationships with the followers help the leader understand their needs. According to Boonyarit, Chomphupart, and Arin (2010), “transformational leaders who seek to understand needs, create positive climates and promote the

feeling of confidence among teachers” (p. 11) which leads to a greater sense of empowerment.

The Empowering Leader

Participative leadership, also called empowering leadership, may be classified as transformational leadership. It includes decision making procedures such as “consultation, joint decision-making, power sharing, decentralization, empowerment, and democratic management” (Yukl, 2011, p. 115). Boonyarit et al. (2010) conclude their study by presenting practical methods an empowering principal can use to improve teachers’ psychological empowerment. These ways include inspiring teachers with a vision but also holding them accountable and setting clear tasks, goals, and roles.

Howard (1998) presents five roles the empowering leader should assume; she believes such a leader should be a visionary, inspirer, team builder, facilitator, and supporter. She explains that today’s world makes it important for employees to take on more responsibilities to face global competition, and “the leader’s role is not just to permit them to take on more but to make sure that they are prepared to handle those responsibilities wisely” (p. 204). She then presents the benefits of empowering leadership to the leader and to the organization suggesting that empowering employees is worth the effort.

Gray and Smith (2005) announce that following the No Child Left behind Act, schools should have a No Teachers Left behind Act to retain qualified teachers and give them opportunities to grow professionally and ultimately feel empowered. It is important to empower students and cater to their needs, but, in order to hire and retain qualified teachers, it is also important to empower teachers and cater to their needs.

Power Struggle

Teacher empowerment requires a principal to practice a significant amount of sharing power with the school teachers. In one definition, leadership is presented as “the way power is used in the process of influencing the actions of others” (Krausz, 1986, p. 90). However, sometimes a power struggle begins between the teachers and the principal.

Employees or subordinates may perceive leader power as positive or negative and accordingly positive or negative consequences become evident:

The leader's power is perceived by the subordinates. The subordinates identify the leader's power and allow the leader to influence their behavior. The leader-subordinate interaction may have either constructive or destructive consequences in an organization. Constructive consequences occur when members of the organization feel competent as professionals and as human beings. Subordinate satisfaction with leadership is high. Destructive consequences occur when members feel powerless, alienated, and oppressed and become passive and combative. Subordinates are dissatisfied with the leadership. (Short & Johnson, 1994, p. 9)

Principals face struggles in sharing power and leadership. With the new movement toward teacher empowerment and establishing democratic school communities, principals might understandably still demonstrate unwillingness to share power with the teachers of the school. However, once principals develop trust in teachers' abilities, they can become more comfortable in sharing their power. Ultimately, principals do not need to share all decisions with teachers. “They do, however, need to share all critical decisions” (Reitzug & O’Hair, 2002, p. 137).

Often, principals are somewhat hesitant in sharing power with the teachers fearing that teachers may abuse this power because “once an individual identifies herself as the leader, there is a tendency to assume entitlement (duty, obligation) to manipulate the power flow” (Conley & Goldman, 1994, p. 5). In order to counter this natural tendency, Conley and Goldman (1994) suggest that principals view themselves as enablers in “sharing power, participation without domination, and facilitation” (p. 7). For this kind of enabling to happen, however, “principals must have confidence in their own leadership skills to encourage and support leadership within the teaching ranks” (Helterbran, 2010, p. 365) or else they would feel threatened by teacher leadership.

Reitzug and O’Hair (2002) also clarify that sharing power “does not mean that principals need to be passive and step into the background” (p. 137). The principals now have a new role of creating a supportive environment that stimulates and empowers teachers to study, inquire, and examine as they partake in decision-making. Moreover, a collective responsibility for all students and school practices is created where the principal and the teachers share power and share responsibility (Reitzug & O’Hair, 2002).

In summary, teacher empowerment has been studied by different researchers in the past several years. Short and Rinehart (1992) have described it as consisting of six dimensions: (a) status, (b) professional growth, (c) self-efficacy, (d) decision-making, (e) impact, and (f) autonomy. The principal has an important role in empowering the teachers by creating a supportive atmosphere at school, but sometimes it is difficult for principals to share power with the teachers fearing they would abuse it. However, the empowering principal (transformational leader) empowers the teachers by supporting, inspiring, and encouraging them.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study was to examine the extent to which the teachers of the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon feel empowered and to compare the results of the principals to that of the teachers. Finally, the study wanted to find out if there is a significant relationship between the six dimensions of empowerment and the teachers' gender, years of experience, and level of education.

Research Design and Method

This study required a mixed-method approach (qualitative and quantitative). It was a survey research in which the opinions of the teachers of the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon were gathered through questionnaires for analysis. A similar questionnaire was given to the five principals of these schools to examine the principals' perceptions of teacher empowerment. The study also included interviews with open-ended questions with the principals to gain insights into what principals think and do about teacher empowerment.

Sample

Through a purposive and convenient non-randomization sampling procedure, the sample that was included in this study was the 143 teachers of the five Armenian Evangelical Schools in Lebanon and the five principals. Table 1 represents a summary of the basic information for the five schools under study.

Table 1

Basic Information about the Schools Participating in the Study

School	Grade Levels	Number of Teaching Staff	Number of Students
School A	Kindergarten through grade 9	23	164
School B	Nursery through grade 12	28	272
School C	Nursery through grade 12	35	315
School D	Nursery through grade 12	30	127
School E	Nursery through grade 12	27	216

All of the five schools participating in the study belong to the Armenian Evangelical community of Lebanon and follow the Lebanese curriculum, in addition to three school subjects: Armenian language, Armenian History, and Christian Education. As a shared goal, these schools work toward preparing Lebanese patriotic citizens who are proud of their Armenian heritage and are raised with Christian values.

Instrumentation

Teacher Questionnaire

The instrument used in this study was The School Participant Empowerment Scale, abbreviated as SPES (Short & Rinehart, 1992). Copies of the questionnaire were given to the teachers to measure their perception of empowerment (refer to Appendix A).

After contacting the authors via email and explaining the purpose of the study, permission to use the instrument was quickly granted. The SPES is a questionnaire that uses a five-point Likert-type rating scale for 38 items (from 1-strongly disagree to 5- strongly agree). These 38 items measure teacher empowerment on six dimensions: (a) status, (b) professional growth, (c) self-efficacy, (d) decision-making, (e) impact, and (f) autonomy. The 38 items are divided among the six dimensions as follows: In terms of status, 6 statements are stated in the SPES which mainly ask about the teachers' perception of professional respect. The dimension of professional growth is presented with four statements such as "I have the opportunity for professional growth." A total of 11 statements present the dimension of self-efficacy which are about the teacher's perception of his or her abilities in helping students learn and making a difference in their lives. The 8 statements presenting the dimension of decision-making tackle different topics such as decisions in curriculum, teacher recruitment, and school budget. Impact is presented with 6 statements about the teachers' perceived influence on school life. As for autonomy, the three statements are specific to scheduling.

Cronbach's coefficient alpha reliabilities for these dimensions are reported by the authors of the instrument (Short & Rinehart, 1992) and presented in Table 2. The reliability scores are well within the acceptable range.

Table 2

Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha Reliabilities for SPES Dimensions

Dimension	Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha Reliabilities
Decision-Making	.89
Professional Development	.83
Status	.86
Self-Efficacy	.84
Autonomy	.81
Impact	.82
Overall Scale	.94

Principal Questionnaire

To understand the principals' perception of the teachers' empowerment, the 38 items of the SPES were rewritten in the third person to refer to the teachers and given to the principals (refer to Appendix B). As such, the teachers' responses and the principals' responses can be compared to reach a conclusion about whether teachers and principals have similar perceptions of teacher empowerment.

Principal Interview

The principals were also asked to sit for a recorded interview of 25-30 minutes and answer some questions about their perceptions of teacher empowerment. The first questions of the interview asked the principals about their leadership style and teacher empowerment in general. The following questions asked for specific details covering the six dimensions of teacher empowerment. The final two questions ask the

principals to think about the advantages and disadvantages of empowering teachers (for the complete list of interview questions, refer to Appendix C).

Procedure

Data Collection

An email was sent to each of the principals of the five Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon with the intention of acquainting them with the purpose of this study. The email first presented the rationale of the study. Then it explained that the teachers would have to fill out a questionnaire about their perception of empowerment in a completely anonymous manner, and the principals would have to fill out a similar questionnaire and then sit for a recorded interview. The email also explained that the study aimed to provide the principals with some insight into their teachers' perception of empowerment.

Four out of the five principals replied to the email within a day, expressing their willingness to help with the study by completing the questionnaires, sitting for an interview, and asking the teachers to complete the questionnaires.

I was notified that the principal of school D was busy transferring his administrative duties to the principal who would be succeeding him. The successor had already been acting as the vice principal for the past several years and had been the acting principal for a year. After contacting the new principal via email, he also expressed willingness to participate in this study.

The questionnaires were placed in envelopes with a letter attached to them (refer to Appendix D) and handed to the five principals. The letter thanked the principals once more for helping with this study and asked for some basic information about the school. The envelope included one copy of the principal questionnaire (refer to Appendix B) and several copies of the teacher questionnaire (refer to Appendix A).

Before the items of the questionnaire, a paragraph explained that that the answers to the questionnaires would remain anonymous. They were, however, asked to provide some basic information such as school name, age, gender, level of education, and years of experience without specifying their names.

After two weeks' time, I contacted the principals again to discuss the method of returning the completed questionnaires and to set a meeting time for the principal interviews. The envelopes with the completed questionnaires were either picked up from the schools or sent by the principals. The schools and participants were alpha coded to maintain confidentiality. The schools were coded A through E, and the participating school principals and school teachers were coded as follows: Principal = P and Teachers = T. Each principal and teacher was also labeled with a number (T1, T2, P1, etc.).

Then, each principal allotted half an hour in his/her schedule for the interview. Each interview was recorded after obtaining the principal's permission. It was difficult for the principal of school E to sit for a face-to-face interview because of the school's distant location. Therefore, only principal E answered the interview questions in written form and sent them back via email. At the end of the study, each of the five principals received the results and the analysis of results of his/her school in an email.

Data Analysis

Once all the questionnaires were returned, I entered the data into SPSS for analysis. To analyze the six dimensions of teacher empowerment in the teacher and principal questionnaires, SPSS Statistics 20 was used. Descriptive analysis helped in finding the frequencies, percentages, and means. The 5-point Likert scale was divided into three quantitative cut-off points as follows:

- Below 3 ($x < 3$) = Disagreement
- Three ($x = 3$) = Neutral
- Above 3 ($x > 3$) = Agreement

These cut-off points helped in analyzing the data by looking at overall mean scores and the mean score for each item on the questionnaires. If the mean score is less than three, then participants do not agree with that item. If the mean score is three, then they are neutral about this item. If the mean score is above three, then the participants agree with this particular item.

Since only 5 schools participated in the study, Pearson correlation was employed. Pearson correlation technique was used in this research to measure the strength of the association of different variables if existing, thus representing any significance or correlation between variables. Only linear relationships can be analyzed with this technique; no causal effects are implied. The correlation between the variables might be positive having a direct significance, it might be indirect or negative, or there might be no correlation whatsoever between the variables revealing that the hypothesis was null. Pearson correlation is an effect size measure:

Positive Effect

- $|r| = .1$ small effect (weak relation)
- $|r| = .3$ medium effect (average)
- $|r| = .5$ large effect (strong relation)

Negative Effect

$|r| = -.n$ (negative variable) means there is an inverse relationship

First, I studied each school separately to explore the teachers' levels of empowerment on each of the six dimensions by calculating the frequencies,

percentages, and means. This was done to understand the teachers' perception of empowerment in each school.

Next, for each school, I compared the teachers' perceptions and the principal's perception to reach a conclusion about whether teachers and principals have similar perceptions of teacher empowerment.

Finally, I studied all the schools as one community taking into consideration the teachers' and principals' perceptions of empowerment and the teachers' personal attributes (gender, level of education, and years of experience), thus looking for a correlation between the six dimensions of empowerment and the variables.

Ethical Considerations

The teachers participating in the study were assured that their answers would remain completely confidential, and, since they did not need to provide names, their answers to the questions remained completely anonymous. They were not questioned or blamed for any answer they provided. They could answer all the questions or refrain from answering any of the questions they did not feel comfortable answering. They were not forced to complete the questionnaires; they could even choose not to return them.

The principals were also assured that their answers to the questions, written and oral, would remain confidential and only be used for the purposes of this study. Furthermore, each of the schools was renamed using the alphabetical letters A through E for higher levels of privacy.

CHAPTER 4

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Once all the questionnaires were collected, the data was entered into SPSS.

The results were then analyzed

1. To examine the teachers' levels of empowerment (on each of the six dimensions) in the Armenian Evangelical schools as a community and separately.
2. To examine the relationship between teachers' perception of empowerment and their personal attributes (gender, level of education, and years of experience) in each school.
3. To compare each principal's answers to that of the teachers' in each school and examine if both parties have similar perceptions of the levels of teacher empowerment.

Return Rates

The total number of teachers working in the Armenian Evangelical schools of Lebanon is 143. The overall return rate for the teachers (N=90) was 62.9 %. The return rate for the principals (N=5) was 100%.

Demographic Characteristics

The demographic characteristics of all the teachers who returned the questionnaires (N=90) are presented in Table 3, and the demographic characteristics of the principals (N=5) are presented in Table 4.

Table 3

Teacher Demographic Characteristics

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	16	18%
	Female	74	82%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	15	16.7%
	6-10	15	16.7%
	11-15	10	11.1%
	16-20	14	15.5%
	21-25	18	20%
	26 and more	18	20%
Level of Education	High School	21	23%
	Vocational/Technical Degree	10	11%
	Bachelor's Degree	45	50%
	Master's Degree	14	16%
	Doctoral Degree	-	-

Table 4

Principal Demographic Characteristics

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	2	40%
	Female	3	60%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	2	40%
	6-10	2	40%
	11-15	-	-
	16-20	-	-
	21-25	1	20%
	26 and more	-	-
Level of Education	High School	-	-
	Vocational/Technical Degree	-	-
	Bachelor's Degree	2	40%
	Master's Degree	2	40%
	Doctoral Degree	1	20%

School A

The demographic characteristics of the teachers of School A are presented in Table 5. Out of 23 teachers, 15 returned the questionnaire (65.22 % return rate). It is worth noting that 10 out of the 15 teachers (67 %) who responded have been teaching at School A for more than 10 years, which could be an indicator of commitment to the school and to the profession of teaching. Unfortunately, the number of males (N=2) who participated from this school is very minimal and does not help generalize gender-based findings.

Table 5

Demographic Characteristics of Teachers of School A

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	2	13.3%
	Female	13	86.7%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	3	20%
	6-10	2	13.3%
	11-15	1	6.7%
	16-20	2	13.3%
	21-25	4	26.7%
	26 and more	3	20%
Level of Education	High School	4	26.7%
	Vocational/Technical Degree	2	13.3%
	Bachelor's Degree	7	46.7%
	Master's Degree	2	13.3%
	Doctoral Degree	-	-

Scores of School A on the Six Dimensions of SPES

The teachers of School A rated their perception of empowerment on the six dimensions presented in the SPES mostly between the “neutral” midpoint and the “agree” point on the five-point scale. They rated the highest levels of empowerment on the dimensions of status and self-efficacy with 4.2 each and autonomy with 4.0. They rated professional growth with 3.7, which can be considered close to the “agree” ranking. The lowest scores were on decision-making (3.3) and impact (3.1).

As for the principal's responses on the SPES, the principal of School A agreed with her teachers on their perception of status (4.2). She gave responses close to the teachers' on the dimensions of professional growth, self-efficacy, decision-making, and impact. The clearest disagreement between the teachers' perception and the principal's perception was on the dimension of autonomy as the teachers scored 4.0 while the principal scored 2.7. Figure 1 compares the scores of the teachers of school A to the scores of the principal of School A.

Analysis of Results of School A

The teachers of school A scored high on the dimensions of status and self-efficacy. This could partly be explained by the fact that 67% of the respondents have more than 10 years of experience and rated self-efficacy at 4, and self-efficacy refers to the teacher's belief in his or her abilities to help students (Short & Rinehart, 1992). The more teachers spend time teaching, the more they gain confidence in their teaching skills and eventually enjoy the professional respect of those around them. Furthermore, based on the interview with the school principal, verbal encouragement and praise are often used at school A, which helps teachers feel appreciated and respected by those around them (Blase & Kirby, 2009). The principal has also tried conducting personal meetings with the teachers to know and appreciate them on a personal level. She further explained that to encourage positive thinking among colleagues, she has placed a box in the staffroom and encourages the teachers to find praiseworthy characteristics in each other, write them down, and drop them in the box. At the end of each month, she chooses a teacher of the month by relying on the statements from the box. As such, the teachers can empower each other and feel that they have a say in this matter, and they practice finding positive attributes in each other, which creates a positive work environment.

Figure 1. Comparison between the scores of the teachers and the scores of the principal at School A.

On the dimension of professional growth, the teachers scored 3.7, and the principal scored 4.0. Both numbers indicate that the teachers and the principal agree to a certain extent that the teachers are empowered in this dimension. The principal explained that the administration, consisting of herself, the academic coordinator, and the school counselor, usually plans need-based workshops at the beginning of each academic year and several others during the school year paying close attention to the timing of the workshops so that they are not scheduled after long, tiring days. She also said that she has been encouraging the teachers to plan and present workshops themselves based on workshops they have attended so the other teachers can benefit as well (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007).

The lowest teacher scores were on decision-making and impact. In terms of decision-making, the principal explained that teachers have complete freedom in what they teach and how they teach it. They also partake in decisions concerning school rules and regulations. The principal used the term “shared leadership” and explained that she is not leading the school alone and that teachers’ opinions are taken into consideration. Often times, the academic coordinator or the school counselor bring the teachers’ ideas or concerns to the principal. However, the reason for the relatively low score on this dimension could be due to the fact that one of the statements on the SPES was “I am involved in school budget decisions,” and the teachers have no say in school budgeting or financial decisions.

As for impact, it is presented on the SPES with five statements that are either about teachers teaching each other (collaborating) or their advice being solicited by other teachers or the principal. The teachers mostly responded with “neutral” or

“disagree” especially on the statements about teachers teaching each other. Even though the principal stated that teachers are encouraged to present workshops to fellow teachers, which is an opportunity to teach each other, their scores could indicate that they either do not take up this opportunity or do not view it as an opportunity to teach others.

It is interesting to note that the scores on the dimension of autonomy differ greatly between teachers’ perception and the principal’s view of teachers’ perception of empowerment. On most of the other dimensions on the SPES, the principal and the teachers scored very close with the principal having a higher notion of teachers’ perception of empowerment, except on the dimension of autonomy. On this dimension, the teachers scored high (4.0), which means they agree that they are empowered through enjoying autonomy in scheduling, while the principal scored low, meaning she disagrees (2.7). The explanation behind this could be that teachers and principals were referring to two different ideas while completing the questionnaires. The teachers might have chosen the “agree” point on the autonomy statements, referring to lesson schedules and plans, while the principal might have chosen the “disagree” point because she was considering the timetables, which she sets at the beginning of each academic year.

The principal concluded that she regularly emphasizes the importance of teamwork and collaboration and tries to empower the school teachers as much as possible. However, she believes that other than a principal’s empowering practices at a school, a teacher’s personality traits and commitment to the profession of teaching should be taken into consideration because these two factors can become a hindrance to the empowerment of a teacher regardless of a principal’s efforts to empower him or her.

When asked about the disadvantages of empowering teachers, the principal of School A explained that teachers should be empowered in the classroom and in their teaching. However, according to her, if teachers are “over-empowered,” especially in areas that do not concern them, their teaching, or their students; they might try to surpass the administration, and that could create some serious problems within the school. This explanation presents the principal’s concern about teachers manipulating the power they are given (Conley & Goldman, 1994).

School B

The demographic characteristics of the teachers of School B are presented in Table 6. Out of 28 teachers, 23 returned the questionnaire (82.14 % return rate). School B had the highest return rate of the five participating schools. It is worth noting that 14 of the teachers (60.9 %) have been teaching at School B for more than 10 years, which could be an indicator of commitment to the school and to the profession, and that 14 (60.9%) do not have a university degree.

Scores of School B on the Six Dimensions of SPES

The teachers of School B rated their perception of empowerment on the six dimensions presented in the SPES mostly between the “disagree” point and the “agree” point on the five-point scale. They rated the highest levels of empowerment on the dimensions of self-efficacy (4.2), status (4.1), and autonomy (4.1). They rated professional growth with 3.6, which can be considered close to the “agree” scale. The lowest scores were on decision-making (3.2) and impact (2.9). The score of the teachers on the dimension of impact is considered to be negative, meaning that they do not feel empowered in this dimension.

Table 6

Demographic Characteristics of Teachers of School B

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	5	21.74%
	Female	18	78.26%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	6	26.1%
	6-10	3	13%
	11-15	3	13%
	16-20	2	8.7%
	21-25	5	21.8%
	26 and more	4	17.4%
Level of Education	High School	6	26.1%
	Vocational/Technical Degree	8	34.8%
	Bachelor's Degree	8	34.8%
	Master's Degree	1	4.3%
	Doctoral Degree	-	-

As for the principal's responses on the SPES, she gave responses close to the teachers' on the dimensions of decision-making (3.1) and autonomy (3.7). However, in terms of status and self-efficacy, her perceptions of the levels of teacher empowerment are lower than the perceptions of the teachers themselves with 3.2 and 3.3 respectively. As for the dimension of professional growth, both the teachers and the principal agree that teachers are empowered in this dimension, but the principal has a higher perception for teacher empowerment than the teachers. The clearest disagreement between the teachers' perception and the principal's perception was on the dimension of impact as the teachers scored 2.9, while the principal scored 3.8. Figure 2 compares the scores of the teachers of school B to the scores of the principal of School B.

Figure 2. Comparison between the scores of the teachers and the scores of the principal at School B.

Analysis of Results of School B

The teachers of school B scored high on the dimensions of self-efficacy (4.2), status (4.1), and autonomy (4.1). Self-efficacy refers to the teacher's belief in his or her abilities to help students (Short & Rinehart, 1992), and the years of experience many of the teachers (60 %) have at School B may contribute to their belief in their abilities. However, the principal of School B rated this dimension of teacher empowerment with a 3.3. The majority of her answers to the 12 statements referring to teacher self-efficacy were on the neutral midpoint 3. This shows a clear inconsistency between the teachers' perceptions and the principal's perception of teacher self-efficacy at this school, meaning that either the principal does not know the teachers well and does not understand their view of themselves or the teachers have rated their self-efficacy higher than it really is.

Status "refers to teacher perceptions that they have professional respect and admiration from colleagues" (Short, 1994, p. 490). Based on the principal's interview, even though she does not praise teachers on a daily basis, she makes sure to highlight the hard work of the teachers from podiums and stages whenever possible. She also stated that on several occasions she had noted certain teachers' skills or subject matter knowledge and praised them. She explained also that in the past even the students were given chances to choose teachers of the month or year.

In the dimension of autonomy, the teachers and the principal agree that the teachers can be considered empowered in this dimension even though the teachers' rated this dimension higher than the principal. The principal explained that she usually sets the timetables or schedules at the beginning of the year, but she does take into consideration the preferences of the teachers especially when they are accompanied with valid reasons. Moreover, teachers have the complete freedom in

planning their lesson plans or schedules within the timetables set by the principal. This means that they can plan the content of the periods any way they want as long as it serves the students and their education.

Another dimension the teachers scored relatively high on is the dimension of professional growth or development. They rated themselves with a 3.6, while the principal rated the teachers' perception of this dimension higher with a 4.0. The principal explained that the school administration usually plans workshops each year in September. These workshops are usually need-based, which is why sometimes different workshops may be prepared for different divisions in the school. Furthermore, to encourage the teachers to attend workshops or seminars during the year, the school pays for half the expenses and may even provide a transportation means. However, the principal described what she thinks teachers desire in terms of professional development. She believes that teachers consider teaching higher grades as one form of promotion and professional development even though she believes teaching the younger classes should be considered more fulfilling and desirable as these are the classes that need qualified teachers, who can prepare the students for the future.

The teachers of school B rated their perception of decision-making with a 3.2, and the principal agrees with them with a score of 3.1. The reason behind this low rating could be because of statements on the questionnaire such as "I am involved in school budget decisions," and "I make decisions about the selection of other teachers for my school." The teachers do not have a say in financial issues, but that is the law according to principal B. They do not have a say in the selection of teachers either because teachers are selected by the principal or by the principal and the academic coordinator together. The teachers, however, do partake in decision-making when it

comes to lesson plans, choice of books, and material to be taught. The principal also explained that she does not make decisions that affect the school life by herself; she usually listens to the teachers' opinions and takes them into consideration when and if necessary.

The dimension in which the teachers of school B rated themselves as not empowered with a negative 2.9 is teacher impact. It is worth noting that the principal's perception of teacher empowerment in this dimension is positive with a 3.8. This indicates that she views the teachers as having more impact on school life than they view themselves to have. Ashton and Webb (1986) explain that when teachers feel that they are doing something valuable with proficiency and are recognized for it, their self-esteem is boosted and they believe they have an impact on school life. In the case of school B, since the verbal recognition is not frequent, based on the interview with the principal, the teachers may not feel that they are doing something of value and influencing the school life.

The principal concluded that she believed that empowered teachers empower their students, and the students' academic results may improve consequently. When asked about the disadvantages of empowerment, the principal of school B explained that for some people, based on their personality types, empowerment could lead to abuse of power. However, she also stated that teachers can take initiatives and propose new ideas. As such, they would have ownership (Blanchard, Carlos, & Alan, 1996) of a project and experience self-empowerment.

School C

The demographic characteristics of the teachers of School C are presented in Table 7. Out of 35 teachers, 17 returned the questionnaire (48.57 % return rate). It is worth noting that the majority of the teachers at school C (94.1%) have university degrees, 29.4% of which also have a Master's degree. This is quite different from the other schools.

Table 7

Demographic Characteristics of Teachers of School C

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	3	17.65%
	Female	14	82.35%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	2	11.76%
	6-10	3	17.65%
	11-15	2	11.76%
	16-20	4	23.52%
	21-25	3	17.65%
	26 and more	3	17.65%
Level of Education	High School	1	5.9%
	Vocational/Technical Degree	-	-
	Bachelor's Degree	11	64.7%
	Master's Degree	5	29.4%
	Doctoral Degree	-	-

Scores of School C on the Six Dimensions of SPES

The teachers of School C rated their perception of empowerment on the six dimensions presented in SPES mostly between the “neutral” midpoint and the “agree” point on the five-point scale. They rated the highest levels of empowerment on the dimensions of status (4.4) and self-efficacy (4.2), followed by autonomy (3.8). The lowest scores were on professional growth (3.4), impact (3.4), and decision-making (3.1).

As for the principal’s responses on the SPES, the principal of School C gave responses close to the teachers’ on the dimensions of status (4.2) and self-efficacy (4.3). On the dimension of autonomy, there is a clear disagreement between the teachers’ perception and the principal’s perception of empowerment as the teachers rated it 3.8 while the principal rated it 3.0. However, on the other dimensions, the principal’s perception of the teachers’ perception of empowerment is higher than that of the teachers’. The principal rated professional growth with 4.5, decision-making with 3.9, and impact with 4.0. Figure 3 compares the scores of the teachers of school C to the scores of the principal of School C.

Analysis of Results of School C

The teachers of school C scored high on the dimensions of status and self-efficacy. This could partly be explained by the fact that 94.1% of the respondents have at least a bachelor’s degree. The university degree may help teachers view themselves as masters of the subject matter they teach, and this gives them confidence that they have the ability and skills to help students. Furthermore, based on the interview with the school principal, verbal encouragement and praise are often used at school C, which helps teachers feel appreciated and respected (Blase & Kirby, 2009). The principal explained that she makes an effort to recognize and appreciate the

Figure 3. Comparison between the scores of the teachers and the scores of the principal at School C.

teachers' hard work; she praises well-decorated bulletin boards, well-prepared events, and good student results both at school and on official exams. She even said that the teachers have come to expect this verbal appreciation regularly from her.

Another dimension the teachers have rated themselves as relatively empowered in is autonomy (3.8) even though the principal's perception of the teachers' empowerment in this dimension is neutral. It is interesting to note that the scores on the dimension of autonomy differ greatly between teachers' perception and the principal's view of teachers' perception of empowerment. The explanation behind this, as with other schools, could be that teachers and principals were referring to two different ideas while completing the questionnaires. The teachers might have chosen the "agree" point on the autonomy statements and referred to lesson schedules and plans, while the principal might have chosen the "disagree" point or the "neutral" midpoint because she was taking into consideration the timetables, which she sets at the beginning of each academic year.

On the dimension of professional growth, the teachers scored 3.4, which is closer to the "neutral" midpoint than the "agree" point; however, the principal rated the teachers' empowerment on this dimension with a 4.5, which indicates that the principal views the teachers as more empowered in this dimension than they view themselves to be. The principal explained that she encourages the teachers to attend workshops, and she works toward introducing changes in the school that help them grow professionally. She also provided an example: she has put together a committee consisting of some of the teachers, and this committee will assess the school development in partnership with an independent consultancy firm. This opportunity, according to her, empowers the members of the committee and adds an experience to their professional lives that can be considered an example of professional growth.

However, the reason behind this disagreement could be the few opportunities for promotion in this field.

On the dimension of teacher impact, the teachers also scored 3.4, similar to the dimension of professional growth, and the principal rated the teachers' perception of empowerment in terms of impact higher than the teachers' own perception. The principal explained that giving the teachers a voice is very important to her, and she tries to always go back to the teachers to take their opinions so they feel they have an influence on the school life. Even though the teachers rated themselves empowered in this dimension, the principal believes them to be more empowered than they view themselves to be. The reason behind this could be because of statements in the questionnaire such as "I have an opportunity to teach other teachers about innovative ideas." The principal did not mention anything about opportunities teachers have to teach each other.

The lowest teacher scores were on the dimension of decision-making (3.1). The principal, however, rated this dimension with a 3.9. She emphasized the importance of transparency and shared agenda and explained that she wants her teachers to feel included in important decisions and develop ownership of changes or new plans in the school. She listed choice of books, classroom decisions, and methods of teaching as areas in which teachers have the freedom of decision-making. Any decision that affects the teachers or their students directly is left to the teachers. Nevertheless, she agreed that teachers do not partake in financial decisions, and the SPES questionnaire mentions financial decisions in one statement and the teachers' mean on that statement is only 1.7, which explains some of the reason for the lower scores in this dimension.

The principal concluded that empowered teachers are happy teachers and that happy teachers are productive teachers. She also emphasized the importance of teamwork at school and inviting teachers to be a part of the big picture so that they can see how important their work is.

When asked about the disadvantages of empowerment, the principal of school C explained that in rare cases empowering teachers had led to disrespecting the principal, especially when she first became principal of school C, but it was not difficult to put an end to that. She also explained that sometimes asking teachers for their opinions could project the false notion that the principal does not know and needs help. However, for principal C these minor disadvantages do not stand in the way of empowering the teachers of school C, and she is not timid when it comes to sharing power and empowering those she works with. This shows that principal C is confident in her own leadership skills and can encourage and support leadership within the teachers (Helterbran, 2010).

School D

The demographic characteristics of the teachers of School D are presented in table 8. Out of 30 teachers, 14 returned the questionnaire (46.7 % return rate). It is worth noting that the majority of the teachers at school D (92.9%) have university degrees, 14.3% of which also have a Master's degree. It is also worth noting that 9 out of the 14 teachers (78.6 %) have been teaching at School D for more than 10 years, which could be an indicator of commitment to the school and to the profession of teaching.

Table 8

Demographic Characteristics of Teachers of School D

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	2	14.3%
	Female	12	85.7%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	1	7.1%
	6-10	2	14.3%
	11-15	1	7.1%
	16-20	3	21.5%
	21-25	2	14.3%
	26 and more	5	35.7%
Level of Education	High School	1	7.1%
	Vocational/Technical Degree	-	-
	Bachelor's Degree	11	78.6%
	Master's Degree	2	14.3%
	Doctoral Degree	-	-

Scores of School D on the Six Dimensions of SPES

The teachers of School D rated their perception of empowerment on the six dimensions presented in SPES mostly between the “neutral” midpoint and the “agree” point on the five-point scale. They rated the highest levels of empowerment on the dimensions of self-efficacy with 4.0, status with 3.8, and autonomy with 3.7. They rated professional growth with 3.5. The lowest scores were on decision-making (3.3) and impact (3.1).

As for the principal's responses on the SPES, the principal of School D gave responses close to the teachers' on the dimensions of status, self-efficacy, and autonomy with 4.3, 3.8, and 4.3 respectively. The clearest disagreement between the

teachers' perception and the principal's perception was on the dimensions of professional growth (4.5) and impact (4.4). In both dimensions, the principal's perception of the level of teacher empowerment is higher than the teachers' perception. As for the dimension of decision-making, the principal's perception (2.9) of teacher empowerment is on the negative side of the spectrum. Figure 4 compares the scores of the teachers of school D to the scores of the principal of School D.

Analysis of Results of School D

The teachers of school D rated self-efficacy (4.0) as the dimension they feel most empowered in. The principal of this school seems to agree with them on this dimension with a 3.8. Since self-efficacy is the teachers' belief in their skills and abilities (Short & Rinehart, 1992), the majority of the teachers of school D having earned a university degree could be the reason behind their confidence in their skills and their good rating of this dimension of empowerment. Moreover, more than 78% of the participating teachers have been working at school D for more than 10 years, and this kind of experience may also add to teachers' self-efficacy.

The teachers of this school also rated themselves as empowered in the dimensions of status and autonomy with 3.8 and 3.7 respectively. In terms of status, the principal explained that verbal appreciation and encouragement are employed at school D as a means of appreciating teachers' knowledge and expertise (Blase & Kirby, 2009). He continued by saying that very few chances are found for teacher promotion based on knowledge or capabilities because a school context does not provide many positions teachers can be promoted to. As for autonomy, the SPES questionnaire concentrated mainly on autonomy in scheduling, and the principal agrees, based on his answers on the questionnaire, that the teachers enjoy a certain degree of autonomy in scheduling lessons and periods.

Figure 4. Comparison between the scores of the teachers and the scores of the principal at School D.

One of the dimensions in which there is a clear disagreement in the levels of teacher empowerment between teachers' perception and the principal's perception is the dimension of professional growth. The teachers scored 3.5 on this dimension, while the principal scored 4.5. The reason behind this disagreement could be, as is the case in other schools, due to the fact that the teachers' perception of their level of empowerment on this dimension can be related to the few opportunities of promotion found in a school context. The principal explained that in the academic field, a teacher cannot expect a promotion or a raise in salary as an indicator of professional growth. He believes that the teaching position in itself is the most important position in a school, more important than an administrative position. According to him, the administration tries to create positions such as coordinators and heads of departments and assigns hard-working, capable teachers for these positions; however, as a teacher, finding ways to improve oneself through attending workshops and reading the latest articles and studies in the field should be considered the best way to grow and develop professionally (Helterbran, 2010). He used the term "self-empowerment" in this dimension as teachers take the initiative and improve their skills.

Another dimension in which there is a clear disagreement between the teachers' perception and the principal's perception is the dimension of impact. The teachers rated themselves with a 3.1, which is very close to the "neutral" midpoint, while the principal rated the teachers' empowerment in this dimension with a 4.4, which indicates that he views the teachers as having more impact on school life than they view themselves to have. The statements on the questionnaire were either about teachers teaching each other (collaborating) or their advice being solicited by other teachers or the principal. The teachers mostly responded with "neutral" or "disagree" especially on the statements about teachers teaching each other. According to the

principal, teachers' opinion is requested and taken into consideration, but he did not mention anything about opportunities given to teachers to teach each other as colleagues.

As for the dimension of decision-making, the teachers rated themselves as somewhat empowered with a 3.3, while the principal gave a negative rating with a 2.9. The reason behind this low rating could be because of statements on the questionnaire such as "I am involved in school budget decisions." The teachers do not have a say in financial issues, but they partake in decision-making when it comes to lesson plans, choice of books, and material to be taught. The principal also explained that the teachers are given a voice in many decisions at school through different committees. He mentioned the faculty council, which consists of the principal and the heads of the departments. This council makes important decisions about students' academic lives, and the principal has a similar, not an overshadowing, voice as that of the other members of the council. Another decision-making committee is the disciplinary committee that makes important decisions about students' behavioral issues or advancement. The social committee makes decisions about the social aspect of the faculty. Finally, teachers can make decisions or put forward proposals through their department meetings. According to the principal, all these committees or departments meet either without the principal or with the principal, but, in the case of the latter, the principal gets one vote, similar to a teacher, and does not impose his decision.

When asked about the disadvantages of empowerment, the principal mentioned abuse of power-sharing and imposing one's opinion on the administration or on his or her colleagues as an example (Conley & Goldman, 1994).

He concluded by stating that communication is key in empowering teachers and that teachers should feel that their opinion is of value to the administration and especially when the decision to be made involves the teacher, the classroom, or the students.

School E

The demographic characteristics of the teachers of School E are presented in table 9. Out of 27 teachers, 21 returned the questionnaire (77.78 % return rate).

Table 9

Demographic Characteristics of Teachers of School E

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	4	19%
	Female	17	81%
Years of Experience	Less than 5	4	19%
	6-10	5	23.8%
	11-15	3	14.3%
	16-20	3	14.3%
	21-25	3	14.3%
	26 and more	3	14.3%
Level of Education	High School	9	43%
	Vocational/Technical Degree	-	-
	Bachelor's Degree	8	38%
	Master's Degree	4	19%
	Doctoral Degree	-	-

It is worth noting that school D had the highest return rate between all the schools participating in this study. It is also worth noting that almost half the staff only has a high school degree, but those are the teachers that have the most experience in the school.

Scores of School E on the Six Dimensions of SPES

The teachers of School E rated their perception of empowerment on the six dimensions presented in SPES mostly between the “neutral” midpoint and the “agree” point on the five-point scale. They rated the highest levels of empowerment on the dimensions of status with 4.1, self-efficacy and autonomy with 4.0 each. They rated professional growth with 3.6. The lowest scores were on impact and decision-making with 3.2 and 3.1 respectively.

As for the principal’s responses on the SPES, the principal of School E agreed with his teachers on their perception of self-efficacy and autonomy as he rated each with a 4.0. He gave similar responses to the teachers’ on the dimensions of impact (3.4) and decision-making (3.4). The clearest disagreement is on the dimensions of professional growth and status. The principal rated the teachers’ perception of empowerment in terms of status (3.5) lower than the teachers’ actual perception; whereas, in the dimension of professional growth, the principal’s perception of teacher empowerment (4.3) is higher than that of the teachers’. Figure 5 compares the scores of the teachers of school E to the scores of the principal of School E.

Figure 5. Comparison between the scores of the teachers and the scores of the principal at School E.

Analysis of Results of School E

The dimension in which the teachers of school D rated themselves as most empowered is the dimension of status (4.1). However, the principal's perception of teacher empowerment in the same dimension is lower (3.5). Status "refers to teacher perceptions that they have professional respect and admiration from colleagues" (Short, *Defining Teacher Empowerment*, 1994, p. 490). On the principal questionnaire, the principal has rated several of the statements with the neutral 3 mark, especially statements that tackle the issue of respect from colleagues. With the neutral responses, the principal might be acknowledging that he does not know the teachers' perceptions of colleague respect. Based on the teachers' responses, they do enjoy collegial respect.

The teachers and the principal of school E agree completely on two dimension of teacher empowerment: self-efficacy (4.0) and autonomy (4.0). Self-efficacy refers to the teacher's belief in his or her abilities to help students (Short & Rinehart, 1992). Based on the results and the principal interview, the teachers at school D have collective efficacy, which can have a positive effect on student results (Brinson & Steiner, 2007). As for autonomy, the principal explained that teachers are autonomous in scheduling and teaching methods. Since all three of the statements in the SPES that refer to autonomy are about scheduling, the teachers and the principal clearly agree that the teachers of this school are empowered in this dimension.

On the dimension of professional growth, the teachers scored 3.6, while the principal rated the teachers' empowerment in this dimension with a 4.3, which indicates that the principal views the teachers as more empowered in this dimension than they view themselves to be. The principal explained that he provides the teachers with opportunities to attend workshops or trainings, to participate in one-on-one

sessions with the psychologist and psychomotor therapist, and to continue their education. As is the case with other schools, teachers' lower perception in this dimension as opposed to the principal's higher perception can be attributed to the teachers' understanding of opportunities for professional growth as being promotions and raises in salaries.

The lowest teacher perceptions of empowerment in school E were in the dimensions of impact (3.2) and decision-making (3.1), and the principal somewhat agrees with them with 3.4 on both dimensions. In terms of impact, the teachers mostly replied on the neutral mark 3 especially on statements about their advice being solicited. The principal also responded with neutral on many of the statements in this dimension agreeing that teachers do not perceive themselves as having influence on school life. As for decision-making, even though the principal explained that teachers were decision-makers in the classroom and school activities, both he and the principal rated teacher empowerment in this dimension close to the neutral midpoint. Statements such as "I make decisions about the selection of other teachers for my school" and "I am involved in school budget decisions" were statements the teachers and the principal disagreed with because recruitment and budgeting are two aspects teachers do not have a say in.

The principal of school E clarified that he tends to lead by example instead of giving orders and that he tries to empower teachers by providing space for personal input. He believes empowered teachers are self-reliant, enthusiastic, and optimistic, and their teaching methods are effective. When asked about the disadvantages of empowering teachers, he explained that teachers may understand empowerment as having authority and would think themselves higher than others creating tension and interpersonal problems within the staff.

Teacher Perception of Empowerment in the Armenian Evangelical Schools

Figure 6 represents a comparison between the perceptions of all the participating teachers of the five Armenian Evangelical schools of Lebanon on the six dimensions of empowerment.

Figure 6. Comparison of all teachers' perception of empowerment.

Based on a quick study of Figure 6, it can be concluded that the means of the teachers of the five participating schools on the six dimensions of empowerment are relatively close. It is also worth mentioning that not one school has the highest means on all the dimensions. Therefore, it cannot be concluded that the teachers of one of these schools are the most empowered in the Armenian Evangelical community. Each principal can compare the means of his/her school to that of the other schools, without

being able to identify the other schools, and form an idea about his/her teachers' perception of empowerment as compared to other schools in the same community.

However, it is worth noting that school C has the highest means in status and impact, while school A has the highest mean in professional growth. School B has the highest mean in autonomy in scheduling, but it has the lowest mean in impact. The means of all the participating teachers of the Armenian Evangelical schools of Lebanon (N=90) on the School Participant Empowerment Scale are presented in Figure 7.

As was the case of the teachers in each school separately, the teachers of the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon as a community agree that they are most empowered in the dimensions of status and self-efficacy followed by autonomy. The lowest scores of empowerment were on the dimensions of impact and decision-making.

Figure 7. Levels of empowerment in the Armenian Evangelical Schools.

Principals' Perception Compared to Teachers' Perception

Figure 8 compares the principals' perception of teacher empowerment to the teachers' perception of their empowerment in the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon. The clearest inconsistencies are clear in the dimensions of professional growth and impact. The reasons behind these inconsistencies are already discussed in each school's analysis of results. The main reason behind the inconsistency in the dimension of professional development is the different interpretations of the term. Professional development could be understood as promotions and raises in salary, or it could be understood as teacher workshops or trainings aimed at improving the teacher's skills. As for impact, even though the principals stated that the teachers have a voice in the school, the teachers do not see that as their advice being solicited by colleagues or the principal.

Principal Interviews

Based on the interviews conducted with the principals, all five principals agreed that teacher empowerment is a must in schools. The principal of school C, for example, said "empowered teachers are productive teachers," while the principal of school B considered teacher empowerment essential to having a positive culture in school.

They also emphasized the importance of communication. The principal of school D explained that communication is key in helping the teachers feel involved. When it comes to decisions that concern the teachers or the students immediately, all the principals agreed that the teachers should be involved. Verbal appreciation is another theme that was repeated in the interviews especially by the principals of schools A, C, and D. They explained that they make it a point to notice teachers' hard work and praise them in public and in private.

Figure 8. Comparison of principal perception to teacher perception in the Armenian Evangelical schools in Lebanon.

Correlations between the Dimensions of Empowerment and Teacher Demographics

Figure 9 presents the correlations between the three variables (gender, level of education, and years of experience) and the six dimensions of teacher empowerment as defined by Short and Rinehart (1992).

Correlations							
		Status	Professional Growth	Self-Efficacy	Decision-Making	Impact	Autonomy
Gender	Pearson Correlation	0.06	0.001	-0.01	0.00	-0.11	-0.20
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.57	1.00	0.92	0.98	0.29	0.06
	N	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00
Level of education	Pearson Correlation	-0.13	0.02	0.13	0.04	0.12	-0.15
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.24	0.85	0.24	0.74	0.26	0.15
	N	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00
Teaching experience	Pearson Correlation	-0.02	0.00	-0.07	0.13	0.02	-0.02
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.88	0.96	0.49	0.22	0.85	0.84
	N	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00

Figure 9. Correlation between dimensions and demographics.

When correlating the six dimensions of empowerment and the three variables, the two-tailed significance is above 0.05 in all cases. This means that there is no significant statistical correlation between the dimensions and the variables. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between teacher empowerment and gender, years of experience, or level of education. As such, it would be interesting to concentrate on what the principals can do to create an environment in which teachers feel empowered.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to measure the extent to which teachers in the five Armenian Evangelical schools in Lebanon feel empowered on six dimensions of empowerment and to compare the teachers' perception of their empowerment to the principals' perception of the teachers' empowerment. The six dimensions of empowerment, as proposed by Short and Rinehart (1992), are (a) status, (b) professional growth, (c) self-efficacy, (d) decision-making, (e) impact, and (f) autonomy.

The study began with four research questions:

- What are the teachers' perceptions of their own levels of empowerment (as measured by The School Participant Empowerment Scale)?

For each of the five schools, the teachers' perceptions of their levels of empowerment were measured using the SPES. The results varied slightly from one school to the other (refer to Figures 6 and 7), however, all were quite positive, with the range being from Neutral to Agree.

- Does gender, level of education, or years of experience play a role in teachers' overall perceptions of empowerment?

The results of the study show that there is no relationship between teachers' perception of empowerment and gender, level of education, or years of experience (refer to Figure 9). This means that other factors may be

contributing to teacher empowerment. Principals can find ways to ensure higher degrees of empowerment.

- Do the teachers and the principals of the Armenian Evangelical schools have similar perceptions of teacher empowerment?

In some dimensions, the teachers and principals of the Armenian Evangelical schools agree such as in the dimensions of status and self-efficacy. In other dimensions such as impact and professional growth, they disagree (refer to Figures 1 through 5 and Figure 8).

- How do the principals view teacher empowerment in the Armenian Evangelical Schools of Lebanon?

Through the principal interviews, it became clear that all the principals of the Armenian Evangelical schools of Lebanon believe that teacher empowerment is important, especially since it is connected to student achievement. However, in some cases, what they considered empowering, the teachers did not see it as empowering. Moreover, in some cases, the principals admitted that there are shortcomings that stand in the face of higher teacher empowerment.

At the end of this study, the principals received the results of their respective schools. Attached to the results was the literature review chapter. As such, the principals could study the results to gain insight into their teachers' perception of empowerment and read the literature review to be further informed about the dimensions of empowerment.

Recommendations for Principals

In terms of self-efficacy, status, and autonomy, the teachers' answers to the statements on the SPES indicate that they feel empowered. However, their answers to

the statements referring to professional growth, decision-making, and impact indicate that teachers do not feel much empowered.

Because of the inconsistency between the principals' responses and the teachers' responses on the dimension of professional growth, principals can make it clear through verbal communication that workshops, seminars, and willingness to continue education are excellent ways for teachers to ensure growth in their careers. Moreover, they can create positions such as coordinators and heads of departments for qualified teachers so that the teachers will have opportunities for promotions and motivation to attend those workshops.

Round-table staff meetings are a great way to involve teachers in the decision-making process. These meetings can give the teachers a voice, and they will feel that they are partaking in decision-making and that they have an influence on school life.

Finally, by experience I know that hard-working teachers need acknowledgement from principals. They need to feel that their effort is noticed and appreciated. An appreciative word goes a long way.

Limitations

The first limitation the study faced was the number of the administrators. Each school had only one principal and one or two coordinators/heads of departments. However, the latter were considered teachers in the study because they also had teaching responsibilities. As such, the number of principals was only 5, while the number of teachers was 143 (90 participated in the study). To obtain more reliable results and get a better insight, the principal interviews were conducted.

Another limitation was the actual usage of the Likert Survey instrument because such instruments of data collection sometimes limit the depth of the respondents' answers, whereas open-ended questions would have allowed for free

expression. Moreover, since the teachers were asked to complete the questionnaires alone and no explanation was provided on the items of the instrument, some items might have been misunderstood. However, for the purposes of the study, for the easy calculation of collected data, and to encourage the teachers to participate, the SPES was employed. As for the likelihood of misunderstanding or misinterpretation, the study relied on the teachers' knowledge and understanding of the English language and the Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha Reliabilities for SPES Dimensions provided by the authors of the instrument (refer to Table 2).

Recommendations for Further Study

Since there was no relation between teacher empowerment and gender, years of experience, or level of education, I recommend another study where the principal variables can be taken into consideration. The principal's years of experience, gender, level of education, or style of leadership might have an influence on teacher empowerment. Moreover, for a better insight into teachers' perception, the proposed study should also interview some of the teachers.

Furthermore, since some of the statements in the SPES were too general and led to different interpretations, another instrument may be devised with clearer statements. For example, the principals agreed with the statement "the teachers have the opportunity for professional growth" while most of the teachers disagreed with the same statement "I have the opportunity for professional growth."

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APPENDIX A
TEACHER QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Teacher,

You are kindly asked to fill out this short questionnaire for a Masters level university study about teacher empowerment. Your answers on this questionnaire will remain completely anonymous but will be considered extremely helpful in completing this study.

Thank you for taking out the time to help
Nara Kouzikian

School name

- School A (Dora)
- School B (Bourj Hamoud)
- School C (Ashrafieh)
- School D (Beirut)
- School E (Anjar)

Gender

- Male
- Female

Age

- 20-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60 and above

Division currently working in

- Kindergarten
- Elementary
- Intermediate
- Secondary

Level of Education

- High School
- Vocational/Technical Degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree

Years of Teaching Experience

- less than 5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 21-25
- 26 and more

*Please rate the following statements in terms of how well they describe your feelings.
Rate each statement on the following scale:*

1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neutral 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1. I am given the responsibility to monitor programs. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 2. I function in a professional environment. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 3. I believe that I have earned respect. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 4. I believe that I am helping kids become independent learners. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 5. I have control over daily schedules. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 6. I believe that I have the ability to get things done. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 7. I make decisions about the implementation of new programs in the school. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |

8. I am treated as a professional.	1	2	3	4	5
9. I believe that I am very effective.	1	2	3	4	5
10. I believe that I am empowering students.	1	2	3	4	5
11. I am able to teach as I choose.	1	2	3	4	5
12. I participate in staff development.	1	2	3	4	5
13. I make decisions about the selection of other teachers for my school.	1	2	3	4	5
14. I have the opportunity for professional growth.	1	2	3	4	5
15. I have the respect of my colleagues.	1	2	3	4	5
16. I feel that I am involved in an important program for children.	1	2	3	4	5
17. I have the freedom to make decisions on what is taught.	1	2	3	4	5
18. I believe that I am having an impact.	1	2	3	4	5
19. I am involved in school budget decisions.	1	2	3	4	5
20. I work at a school where kids come first.	1	2	3	4	5
21. I have the support and respect of my colleagues.	1	2	3	4	5
22. I see students learn.	1	2	3	4	5
23. I make decisions about curriculum.	1	2	3	4	5
24. I am a decision maker.	1	2	3	4	5
25. I am given the opportunity to teach other teachers.	1	2	3	4	5
26. I am given the opportunity to continue learning.	1	2	3	4	5
27. I have a strong knowledge base in the areas in which I teach.	1	2	3	4	5
28. I believe that I have the opportunity to grow by working daily with students.	1	2	3	4	5
29. I perceive that I have the opportunity to influence others.	1	2	3	4	5
30. I can determine my own schedule.	1	2	3	4	5
31. I have the opportunity to collaborate with other teachers in my school.	1	2	3	4	5
32. I perceive that I make a difference.	1	2	3	4	5
33. Principals, other teachers, and school personnel solicit my advice.	1	2	3	4	5
34. I believe that I am good at what I do.	1	2	3	4	5
35. I can plan my own schedule.	1	2	3	4	5
36. I perceive that I have an impact on other teachers and students.	1	2	3	4	5
37. My advice is solicited by others.	1	2	3	4	5
38. I have an opportunity to teach other teachers about innovative ideas.	1	2	3	4	5

APPENDIX B
PRINCIPAL QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Principal,

You are kindly asked to fill out this short questionnaire for a Masters level university study about teacher empowerment. Your answers on this questionnaire will remain completely anonymous but will be considered extremely helpful in completing this study.

Thank you for taking out the time to help
Nara Kouzikian

*Please rate the following statements in terms of how well they describe your feelings.
Rate each statement on the following scale:*

1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neutral 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree

- | | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1. The teachers are given the responsibility to monitor programs. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 2. The teachers function in a professional environment. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 3. The teachers believe that they have earned respect. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 4. The teachers believe that they are helping kids become independent learners. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 5. The teachers have control over daily schedules. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 6. The teachers believe they have the ability to get things done. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 7. The teachers make decisions about the implementation of new programs in the school. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 8. The teachers are treated as professionals. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 9. The teachers believe they are very effective. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 10. The teachers believe that they are empowering students. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 11. The teachers are able to teach as they choose. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |

12. The teachers participate in staff development.	1	2	3	4	5
13. The teachers make decisions about the selection of other teachers for the school.	1	2	3	4	5
14. The teachers have the opportunity for professional growth.	1	2	3	4	5
15. The teachers have the respect of their colleagues.	1	2	3	4	5
16. The teachers believe that they are involved in an important program for children.	1	2	3	4	5
17. The teachers have the freedom to make decisions on what is taught.	1	2	3	4	5
18. The teachers believe that they are having an impact.	1	2	3	4	5
19. The teachers are involved in school budget decisions.	1	2	3	4	5
20. The teachers work at a school where kids come first.	1	2	3	4	5
21. The teachers have the respect and support of their colleagues.	1	2	3	4	5
22. The teachers see students learn.	1	2	3	4	5
23. The teachers make decisions about curriculum.	1	2	3	4	5
24. The teachers are decision makers.	1	2	3	4	5
25. The teachers are given the opportunity to teach other teachers.	1	2	3	4	5
26. The teachers are given the opportunity to continue learning.	1	2	3	4	5
27. The teachers have a strong knowledge base in the areas in which they teach.	1	2	3	4	5
28. The teachers believe that they have the opportunity to grow by working daily with students.	1	2	3	4	5
29. The teachers perceive that they have the opportunity to influence others.	1	2	3	4	5
30. The teachers can determine their own schedules.	1	2	3	4	5
31. The teachers have the opportunity to collaborate with other teachers in my school.	1	2	3	4	5
32. The teachers perceive that they make a difference.	1	2	3	4	5
33. School personnel, other teachers, and I solicit teachers' advice.	1	2	3	4	5
34. The teachers believe that they are good at what they do.	1	2	3	4	5
35. The teachers can plan their own schedule.	1	2	3	4	5
36. The teachers perceive that they have an impact on other teachers and students.	1	2	3	4	5
37. The teachers' advice is solicited by others.	1	2	3	4	5
38. The teachers have opportunities to teach other teachers about innovative ideas.	1	2	3	4	5

APPENDIX C
INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Interview Questions for the School Principals

- How would you describe your leadership style?
- Do you believe you empower your teachers? If yes, how do you empower them?
- In what areas do the teachers of this school partake in decision-making? In what areas do they have control?
- Do you provide the teachers with opportunities for professional growth? What are they?
- What do you do to make teachers feel that their knowledge and expertise are appreciated and that they are helping the students learn?
- Are there things teachers can do to feel more empowered?
- What are advantages of empowering teachers?
- What are disadvantages of empowering teachers?

APPENDIX D

LETTER ATTACHED TO QUESTIONNAIRES

Dear Principal,

Thank you for taking out the time to help with this study.

In this envelope, you will find one copy of the principal's questionnaire for you and several copies of the teacher's questionnaire for the teachers.

Once filled out, please put the questionnaires back in this envelope.

Please fill out the missing information below.

For the school principal

School _____

Year founded _____

Number of teaching staff _____

Number of students _____

For the researcher

Date of drop off _____

Date of pick up _____

Number of questionnaires initially in the envelope _____

Number of questionnaires filled out and returned _____

RESUME

Education	<p>2011- 2017 Middle East University Sabtieh MA in Educational Leadership</p> <p>2005-2009 Lebanese University, Humanities Fanar License in Teaching English Language and Literature</p> <p>2004-2005 High School of SineFil Sin el Fil Bach II, Economics and Sociology</p>
Professional experience	<p>2016- Armenian Evangelical Shamlan School Bourj Hammoud Academic Coordinator of the Elementary Division</p> <p>2015-2016 Middle East University Sabtieh Instructor of Basic Grammar Course (Beginners' English)</p> <p>2012-2016 Jesus and Mary School Rabweh Teacher of English Language (Grades 7 and 8)</p> <p>2009-2012 Eastwood College Mansourieh Class Teacher (KG2)</p> <p>2008-2009 Greater Beirut Evangelical School (GBES) Sioufi Class Teacher (KG1)</p> <p>2008-2011(summers) Armenian Evang Emmanuel Church Dora Coordinator and director of summer school activities</p> <p>2006-2008 Armenian Evangelical School Trad Bourj Hamoud Teacher of English Language for Elementary Classes (Grades 1 - 4)</p>
Volunteer experience	<p>2003-2007 Armenian Evangelical Emmanuel Church Dora Sunday School Teacher</p>